

The Cultural Factors in Early Postpartum Care Society in Manurunge Village, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Post-partum is the period after delivery finished up 6 weeks or 42 days. Once during childbirth, reproductive organs will undergo changes as before pregnancy. To know the cultural factor in postnatal care community in Manurunge village, south Sulawesi, Indonesia. This type of research is qualitative research. The participants were 10 peoples including the mother postpartum / breastfeeding, midwives and leader community. The research shows that 1) Care during childbirth is very important in Maintaining the health of mother and baby both physically and psychologically. Puerperal period is a period of no less importance to the pregnancy, because the baby's life is depending on their mother. 2) Manurunge Village community in postnatal care including a) tied a cloth on the abdomen when after birth, b) Do not lift the burden is too heavy, c) Push breast while showering, 4) Mothers should be encouraged shower 2 times a day and evening, 3) It is recommended consuming foods such as vegetables and legumes such as leaves of kale and peanuts to help augment milk production of mother. 4) matters/things become taboo in the puerperium namely: a) Do not eat maize, hot food, acidic foods, and water ice, c) Do not take the child out of the house up to 40 days because it may cause the disease to the children or entitled to be follow spirits, 5) an important thing to do is aqiqah or Islamic tradition. The conclusion of this research is: there are still many postnatal care cultures are applied in Manurunge village, south Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Keywords: Culture, Society, Care Postpartum Period.

INTRODUCTION

Reproductive health in women is an issue of sexuality and reproduction related to antenatal care, childbirth, and post treatment of maternity. The number of maternal and infant mortality is an indicator of reproductive health which Indonesia is still high compared with other countries. Previous research has suggested that socio-demographic and cultural factors influence the high rate of maternal and infant mortality (Suryawati, 2007). Puerperal or post-partum is the period after delivery finished up 6 weeks or 42 days. Once during childbirth, reproductive organs will slowly change as before pregnancy. During the postpartum period should receive more attention due to the maternal mortality rate of 60% occurred in the postpartum period. In the maternal mortality rate (MMR) is the cause of many women died from a cause of lack of attention to post partum women (Maritalia, 2012); (Damaiyanti, 2014).

WHO noted that in 2017 nearly 800 (99%) of women die every day due to complications during pregnancy and childbirth and occurs in the developing countries. According to WHO report in 2018 the maternal mortality rate is high, namely 420 per 100,000 live births, compared with other ASEAN countries, (WHO, 2019). Refer to the Demographics health Indonesia (IDHS) in 2007 showed that Indonesian ranks is in the third position after Laos and Cambodia as ASEAN countries with maternal mortality ratio (MMR) is the highest is 228 / 100,000 live births and the government expects by 2017

that number can be reduced to 102 / 100,000 live births (Ministry of Health, Republic of Indonesia, 2013), but the 2018 survey results proves SDKI opposite number AKI increase be 359 / 100,000 live births (Ministry of Health, 2014)

Service data KesehatanProvinsi South Sulawesi diperolehangka 2016 amounted to 142 maternal deaths penyebabterbanyakperdarahan 39 (27.4%), infeksi20 people (14%), perineal wound pain 29 (20.4%), other danpenyebab 54 people (38%). 2017 acquired maternal mortality rate of 124 the most common cause of bleeding 25 (20.2%), infection 8 (6.4%), perineal wound pain 23 (18.5%), and other causes 36 people (29 , 03%).In 2018 obtained the maternal mortality rate by 124 people the most common cause of bleeding 25 (20.2%), infection 8 (6.4%), Luka perineum 23 people (18.5%), and other causes 36 (29.03 %). (ProfilDinkes ProvinsiSul-Cell, 2016). (www.dinkessul-cell/co.id, accessed on June 4, 2019). Data DHO Bone in 2016 the number of puerperal women as much as 13 666 people (92.30%), in 2017 as many as 13.015 people (89.70%). While in 2018 the number of puerperal women as much as 13 187 people (90.89%), (Data DHO. Bone, 2019).

According to data obtained from health centers Ulaweng, in 2016 the number of puerperal women as much as 354 people (71.5%), in 2017 the number of puerperal women as much as 419 people (86.93%). While in 2018 the number of puerperal women 383 votes (79.30%), (PHC Data Ulaweng, 2019). Cultural society in postnatal care such as; prohibition to leave the house for 40 days, told to lie down on a gurney that elevated essentially by hot bricks, his feet on his back and clenched, arms should not be raised above the head as well as her mother look after her, while overseeing that postpartum women are still following the instructions on the position of the feet and how to lay down once in a while should be changed so that the whole body is warmed woman.(Iqbal, 2012); (Jannah 2011).

Beliefs and cultural beliefs against post partum maternal care are still encountered in many communities. They believe culture maternal care after birth can have a positive impact and benefit for them. This is evident from research conducted by Andhra Pradesh at 100 mothers in the postpartum period Tirupati. From his research in getting a lot of trust and cultural beliefs maternal care post partum, including restrictions on fluid intake, food is limited and can only eat vegetables, should not bathe, diet food, not allowed out of the house, using the footwear, use octopus, not allowed to sleep in the daytime they even believe Colostrum is not good for children, (Bhvaneswari, 2013).

In connection with the data in the authors are motivated to study further in a final report entitled "Cultural Factors in Postpartum Period Care in Rural Communities Manurunge Ulaweng District of Bone County".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location, Research Subjects

The research was conducted inManurunge Village District of UlawengBone district, while the research subjects by 10 informants.

1. The inclusion criteria
 - a. Pregnant women are willing to be interviewed
 - b. Village midwives are willing to be interviewed
 - c. Community leaders willing to be interviewed
 - d. A villager manurunge
2. exclusion criteria
 - a. pregnant women are not willing to be interviewed
 - b. midwives are not willing to be interviewed
 - c. community leaders are not willing to be interviewed: Shaman

Data collection procedures

1. doing observations

Observation is a method of collecting data using observations of the research object

which can be carried out directly or indirectly. The function of observation in this study is used to directly observe the District Maroanging Village culture Sibulue in the face of pregnancy.

2. interviews

The interview is the interview data collection techniques in one or more of the persons concerned. In this interview, the author uses two types, namely structured interviews and unstructured interviews. Writers do this method by conducting interviews with the District Maroanging Sibulue Village community with regard to the behavior of people in the face of pregnancy.

3. Documentation

Documentation method is the method used to find the data that are authentic documentation, whether the data is a diary, memory or other important notes. As is the document here is the data or documents are written. This documentation method I use to collect data has not been collected through previous data collection tool.

Data Analysis

1. Data Reduction

Data reduction is a method of data processing, where the data obtained from the field which is quite a lot, it should be noted carefully and in detail. Information from the field as a raw material to be summarized, more systematically arranged and attached critical points, making it easier to be known and understood to derive a conclusion. (Ari Setiawan, 2013)

2. Presentation of Data

In this qualitative study, data presentation is done in the form of a brief description, chart, relations between categories and the like. The most often used to present data in qualitative research is the narrative text. By displaying the data, it will be easier to understand what is happening, to plan further work. (Notoatmodjo 2010).

3. Conclusion

Conclusions in qualitative research are preliminary conclusion expressed still provisional and will change if no strong

evidences that support the next gathering stage. But if the conclusions put forward in the early stages, supported by evidence that reliable and consistent when researchers returned spaciousness of collecting data, the conclusions expressed the conclusion of credible (trustworthy). (Sugyono, 2014)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Future Care Ruling

The majority of mothers in the village of the District Manurunge Ulaweng know about postnatal care. Postnatal care is very important to maintaining the health of mother and baby both physically and psychologically, Post partum/ breast-feeding is a period of no less importance to the pregnancy, because the baby's life is still very dependent on his mother.

2. Tradition Mabbekkeng (Tie cloth) in the stomach after giving birth

Village Community Manurunge in postnatal care is still a tradition of mabbekkeng (tie cloth on the abdomen) which aim to facilitate and increase mother's milk (ASI). Usually the fabric used on the hood or scarf made of silk. In view bengkung health or stagen made of fabric that is very long, which is used in a way stomachs mother tightly wrapped. As for the point that is accelerating the stomach back original size after childbirth. But now use bengkung or stagen is not recommended because person wrapped around the mother's abdomen too tight so it can make a mother difficult to move and difficult to breathe, and especially in women who are going through the process operation is not recommended for used bengkung or stagen because of scar surgery can open back. Now women are more obligation to do gymnastics parturition after delivery by pressing on breathing exercises and stomach. Namesake is also much more helpful in restoring the firmness of the abdomen after childbirth,

3. Tradition drink Herb after birth

Manurunge Village Community relating to consume nostrum after delivery is not done. Because they realize that taking

drugs other than prescription will have an impact for the mother and baby.

4. The tradition of a warm bath after birth
Manurunge Village Community relating to the tradition of a warm water bath was made public because it is the recommendation of family and health professionals aimed at keeping the vital organs after giving birth to a speedy recovery and dry.

5. Tradition does not leave the house before 40 days after birth

Manurunge Village Community with regard to tradition does not leave the house before 40 days after birth is still done partly community. Because most people believe before 40 days still smelled blood nursing mothers and children should not be out because they span disturbances delicate creatures. Based on the medical view is not justified in the theory of puerperal women's health are forbidden to leave the house for <40 days. Research shows that mothers who have given birth or are expected to move gradually done (early mobilization) cure process to take place quickly.

6. Tradition wake the child with leaf Lontar

Manurunge Village Community with regard to tradition wake the child with Lontar Leaf is not done because people no longer believe in it. Because they conscious if the child would certainly wake up hungry baby. Pediatricians say that infant nutrition should be met by way of suckle baby on demand that is breastfeeding every two hours. So when the baby to sleep through than 2 hours, it can be woken up for feedings.

7. Things are becoming ban during breastfeeding

Village Community Manurunge things became ban during pregnancy that is forbidden to liftweight-weight because it can cause breast swelling. Apart from that forbidden to eat hot food because it can cause gas which is not good for milk production. According to the medical view that the mother during childbirth is not allowed to lift heavy loads, the reason

because the condition of the uterus has not fully recovered, and the uterine muscles will tense when used to pick-up a heavy load, and can cause bleeding.

CONCLUSION

Postnatal care is very important to Maintaining the health of mother and baby both physically and psychologically, Post partum / breastfeeding is a period of no less importance to the pregnancy, because the baby's life dependents on his mother. There are some postnatal traditions that the people of manurung village generally doing namely, mabbekeng, no consuming medicine, drinking warm water and not leave the house before 40 days after birth.

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